

Thermodynamics of Ion Exchange Equilibria Involving Fe²⁺ Ion on Na⁺—Montmorillonite

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Manuscript received 2 April 1974; revised 5 November 1974; accepted 1 March 1975

An attempt has been made to predict the mechanism of Fe²⁺-Na⁺ exchange on montmorillonite with the help of thermodynamic parameters. From the exchange isotherms at 30° and 60° the free energy, enthalpy and entropy for the exchange reactions were calculated. The isotherms, and free energy changes indicated a preference of Na⁺ ions for the clay phase. The activity coefficients of the adsorbed ions were also obtained and the excess thermodynamic functions calculated from them. These terms explained the deviation of the clay system from ideality.

THE cation exchange properties of silicate minerals have been of considerable interest both for theoretical and practical reasons. Montmorillonite is an important ion exchange and absorbent material. A large amount of work has been reported on its ion exchange properties. Iron is an important micronutrient and plays a useful role in soil enzyme and plant nutrition. It occupies an important structural position in some of the silicate minerals. The ion exchange reactions of iron have been studied by several workers. In view of the unusual exchange affinities shown by iron, a thermodynamic study of the adsorption of iron on sodium montmorillonite was considered worthwhile. Thermodynamic formulations of previous workers¹⁻⁵ have been used and an attempt made to arrive at a suitable mechanism of Fe²⁺-Na⁺ exchange in montmorillonite with the help of thermodynamic functions and the surface activity coefficients of exchangeable Na⁺ and Fe²⁺.

Experimental

The clay used was montmorillonite from Amori, Mississippi. It was dispersed in distilled water and centrifuged. To obtain < 2μ Na⁺-montmorillonite it was equilibrated⁶ with 2N NaCl and a small quantity of 0.1N HCl for half an hour and the supernatant salt solution decanted. This treatment was repeated three times and chloride ions removed from the Na⁺-montmorillonite suspension by washing with distilled water and alcohol until the clay dispersed and the conductivity of the aqueous suspension was of the same order as that of distilled water (10⁻⁵ mhos/cm). It was then quickly used for the cation-exchange experiments to avoid any ageing effects. The concentration of the suspension was 5.40 g/litre.

For the determination of the exchange isotherms the clay suspension was buffered with very dil. HNO₃. This also eliminated the possibility of hydroxide precipitation. 20.0 ml each of sodium montmorillonite

clay suspension was taken in several stoppered test tubes, and varying amounts of 0.02N ferrous sulphate solution added and the mixture adjusted to a constant volume with distilled water. The tubes was shaken for three hours at 30° ± 0.1° in the first set of experiments and 60° ± 0.1° in the second set of experiments in a thermostatic waterbath. The mixtures were then centrifuged and the Na⁺ and Fe²⁺ in the supernatant liquid estimated. Na⁺ was measured flame-photometrically, and Fe²⁺ colorimetrically with Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20 at 510 nm using orthophenanthroline⁷ as colour reagent. The pH values of these equilibrium solutions were found to vary between 3.0 to 3.3. The CEC of montmorillonite was measured by the ammonium-acetate method of Jackson. The corresponding concentrations for Na⁺ in clay phase were obtained by difference (CEC-concentration of the cation in the supernatant liquid) and that for Fe²⁺ from Fe²⁺ added minus the cation in the supernatant liquid.

Results and Discussion

The interaction between the Fe²⁺ ions in solution and the Na⁺ ions on the clay surface may be represented by the equation :

The barred quantities refer to the equivalent concentrations of the ion concerned in the clay phase and C_{Fe} and C_{Na} the electrolyte concentration in the solution. The equivalent ionic fractions of Fe²⁺ and Na⁺ in montmorillonite and in the solution were calculated from the expressions⁸

$$\bar{X}_{Fe} = \frac{\bar{C}_{Fe}}{C}, \quad X_{Fe} = \frac{C_{Fe}}{C}, \quad \bar{X}_{Na} = \frac{\bar{C}_{Na}}{C}, \quad X_{Na} = \frac{C_{Na}}{C} \quad \dots (2)$$

where \bar{C} and C were the total electrolyte concentrations in the clay and solution phases respectively. The values obtained both at 30° and 60° are given in Table 1. The data yielded the exchange isotherms vide Fig. 1. The isotherms were of the Langmuir type, showed a strong preference by montmorillonite for Na⁺ as against Fe²⁺ with no selectivity reversal and depended on temperature; the affinity for Fe²⁺ increasing with a rise in temperature.

To examine the interaction in the liquid and clay phases represented by equation (1) and taking the ratio of the activity coefficients in the liquid phase in the range of concentration studied by us as unity⁹, the selectivity coefficients at various values of \bar{X}_{Fe} were calculated from the expression

$$K_c = \frac{(\bar{X}_{Fe})(X_{Na})^2}{(\bar{X}_{Na})^2 (X_{Fe})} \quad \dots (3)$$

A plot of the values of K_c obtained at different temperatures (Table 1) for Na⁺-Fe²⁺ exchange in 0.54% montmorillonite suspensions is given in Fig. 2. The selectivity coefficient, on an average, showed a decrease with increasing concentration of Fe²⁺ on montmorillonite. The variation in the selectivity coefficient with composition of the surface phase (\bar{X}_{Fe}) indicated that there were significant interactions between the neighbouring ions on the surface of montmorillonite due to differences in the electrostatic attraction or binding energy of the exchange sites arising from tetrahedral vs octahedral substitution.

For a further study of the affinity the thermodynamic equilibrium constant K was calculated by the equation

$$\ln K = (Z_A - Z_B) + \int_0^{0.25} \ln K_c d\bar{X}_{Fe^{2+}} \quad \dots (4)$$

where Z_A and Z_B were the valences of the competing ions. The integral was evaluated from the area under the curves (Fig. 2) using the trapezoidal rule. The value of K at 30° was lower than at 60° (Table 2) indicating that the affinity of Fe²⁺ for montmorillonite increased with a rise in temperature, a result in accordance with the deductions drawn from the nature of adsorption isotherms.

The Gibbs free energy change for the exchange reaction was calculated using the relation

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K \quad \dots (5)$$

The standard enthalpy change ΔH° was calculated from the Vant' Hoff isochore

$$\ln \left(\frac{K_{T_2}}{K_{T_1}} \right) = -\frac{\Delta H^\circ}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_2} - \frac{1}{T_1} \right) \quad (6)$$

and the standard entropy change by the equation

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad \dots (7)$$

The thermodynamic values obtained are summarized in Table 2. The values were qualitative and could not be calculated with the desired accuracy

Fig. 1. Exchange isotherm of iron on sodium montmorillonite at different temperatures.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF EQUIVALENT IONIC FRACTIONS OF IRON AND SELECTIVITY QUOTIENTS AT 30° AND 60° FOR THE Fe²⁺ EXCHANGE WITH SODIUM-MONTMORILLONITE

Sl. No.	X _{Fe}	X _{Fe}	30°			
			\bar{X}_{Na}	X _{Na}	K _c	log K _c
1.	0.125	0.520	0.874	0.479	0.07220	-1.142
2.	0.177	0.784	0.822	0.215	0.01540	-1.813
3.	0.205	0.872	0.794	0.127	0.00600	-2.222
4.	0.219	0.913	0.780	0.087	0.00300	-2.523
5.	0.231	0.936	0.768	0.063	0.00160	-2.796
6.	0.239	0.953	0.760	0.045	0.00083	-3.081
7.	0.205	0.962	0.809	0.037	0.00044	-3.357
8.	0.231	0.965	0.768	0.034	0.00047	-3.328
9.	0.239	0.968	0.760	0.031	0.00041	-3.387
10.	0.231	0.967	0.768	0.032	0.00039	-3.409
11.	0.254	0.974	0.745	0.025	0.00027	-3.569
12.	0.238	0.977	0.760	0.022	0.00021	-3.678
Sl. No.	X _{Fe}	X _{Fe}	60°			
			\bar{X}_{Na}	X _{Na}	K _c	log K _c
1.	0.116	0.599	0.883	0.400	0.03970	-1.401
2.	0.156	0.820	0.843	0.179	0.00860	-2.066
3.	0.179	0.885	0.820	0.114	0.00390	-2.409
4.	0.194	0.918	0.805	0.081	0.00210	-2.678
5.	0.203	0.931	0.796	0.068	0.00160	-2.796
6.	0.210	0.953	0.789	0.046	0.00074	-3.131
7.	0.182	0.960	0.817	0.039	0.00041	-3.387
8.	0.208	0.964	0.791	0.035	0.00040	-3.398
9.	0.216	0.965	0.783	0.034	0.00042	-3.377
10.	0.206	0.968	0.793	0.031	0.00033	-3.482
11.	0.233	0.968	0.766	0.031	0.00040	-3.398
12.	0.209	0.974	0.790	0.025	0.00020	-3.699

because of the uncertainties about the energy of hydration of adsorbed ions. As a matter of fact ΔH° values included the enthalpies of hydration, dilution, mixing and exchange.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC VALUES FOR THE Fe²⁺ EXCHANGE WITH SODIUM MONTMORILLONITE AT 30° AND 60°

Thermodynamic parameter	Value at 30°	Value at 60°
K	0.176	0.192
ΔG° cal/mole	+1050.6	+1094.3
ΔH° cal/mole		+ 609.1
ΔS° cal/mole		- 1.46

Positive ΔG° values both at 30° and 60° indicated that Fe²⁺ had a smaller preference for the montmorillonite surface than Na⁺ in accordance with the earlier assumptions.

The reaction was attended by positive enthalpy effects i.e., the adsorption increased with a rise in temperature, a fact in accordance² with our observations. The increase in enthalpy pointed¹⁰ that Fe²⁺ was less strongly bound with the clay than Na⁺ and the exchange of Na⁺ with Fe²⁺ may not be easy in the above system.

The exchange was also ruled by entropy effects. The preference for Na⁺ could be due to entropy effects. The decrease in entropy accompanying the exchange of Na⁺ by Fe²⁺ ions could be a consequence of the different double layer¹¹ structures of Na⁺ and Fe²⁺ ions. With Na⁺ ions the double layer was more extended and the distribution of cations above the negative montmorillonite surface was more diffuse than in the case of Fe²⁺ ions which might be arranged in a more ordered structure.

The activity coefficients of the cations at the surface were calculated from the following relations^{8,4}

$$\ln f_{Na} = \bar{X}_{Fe} \ln K_c - \int_0^{\bar{X}_{Fe}} \ln K_c d\bar{X}_{Fe} \quad \dots (8)$$

and

$$\ln f_{Fe} = (\bar{X}_{Fe}^{-1}) \ln K_c - \int_0^{\bar{X}_{Fe}} \ln K_c d\bar{X}_{Fe} \quad \dots (9)$$

The values obtained are given in Table 3. Large values were obtained for the surface phase activity coefficients of Fe²⁺ at the clay surface both at 30° and 60°. High values for activity coefficients in solid phase have been reported by other workers^{4,12} also in case of ions with unlike changes interacting on non-ideal surfaces. Such values of activity coefficients, therefore, were indicative of a marked heterogeneity at the clay surface with significant interactions between the Na⁺ and Fe²⁺ ions at the neighbouring sites of the surface.

TABLE 3—THE SURFACE PHASE ACTIVITY COEFFICIENTS FOR DIFFERENT Na⁺-Fe²⁺ COMPOSITIONS AT THE CLAY SURFACE AT 30° AND 60°

Sl. No.	Value at 30°			Value at 60°		
	\bar{X}_{Fe}	f _{Na}	f _{Fe}	\bar{X}_{Fe}	f _{Na}	f _{Fe}
1.	0.125	0.80	11.11	0.116	0.79	19.98
2.	0.177	0.63	40.91	0.156	0.64	74.64
3.	0.205	0.53	88.45	0.179	0.57	131.80
4.	0.219	0.46	155.50	0.194	0.51	241.00
5.	0.231	0.39	246.80	0.203	0.48	302.00
6.	0.239	0.34	413.10	0.210	0.41	549.50
7.	0.254	0.26	964.70	0.216	0.36	851.10

The excess thermodynamic functions play an important part in expressing the deviation of a heterogeneous system from ideality. The excess thermodynamic functions for the formation of a heteroionic

Na⁺-Fe²⁺ exchanger were calculated from the activity coefficients. Thus, the excess free energy of mixing ΔG_m^x was calculated from the relationship¹³

$$\Delta G_m^x = RT(\bar{X}_{Fe} \ln f_{Fe} + \bar{X}_{Na} \ln f_{Na}) \quad \dots (10)$$

The excess enthalpy of mixing was calculated using the expression⁴

$$\Delta H_m^x = -RT^2 \left[\bar{X}_{Fe} \left(\frac{\delta \ln f_{Fe}}{\delta T} \right) + \bar{X}_{Na} \left(\frac{\delta \ln f_{Na}}{\delta T} \right) \right] \quad \dots (11)$$

The excess entropy of mixing was then calculated by the equation

$$\Delta G_m^x = \Delta H_m^x - T \Delta S_m^x \quad \dots (12)$$

The values are tabulated in Table 4.

The excess free energy of mixing plotted against equivalent ionic fraction in the clay is given in Fig. 3. It was positive and increased with concentration of the Fe²⁺ ion at both temperatures. This was indicative¹⁴ of the fact that the heterogeneous mixture of Na⁺ and Fe²⁺ phases on the clay surface was less stable as compared to the pure homoionic forms i.e., the deviation from ideality occurred in the sense of a less stable mixture. This presumably was due to a variation in the hydration state of the randomly interstratified Na⁺ rich and Fe²⁺ rich layers on the montmorillonite surface.

TABLE 4—THE EXCESS FREE ENERGIES, ENTHALPIES AND ENTROPIES OF MIXING, ΔG_m^x , ΔH_m^x , ΔS_m^x FOR Na⁺-Fe²⁺ EXCHANGE ON MONTMORILLONITE AT 30° AND 60°

30°				
Sl. No.	\bar{X}_{Fe}	ΔG_m^x	ΔH_m^x	ΔS_m^x
1.	0.125	65.54	-383.67	-1.48
2.	0.177	167.14	-749.07	-3.02
3.	0.205	250.96	-822.15	-3.54
4.	0.219	302.57	-1032.12	-4.40
5.	0.231	337.18	-1205.82	-5.09
6.	0.239	377.88	-1205.82	-5.23
7.	0.254	448.37	-1607.76	-6.78
60°				
1.	0.116	94.83	-441.34	-1.61
2.	0.156	199.60	-794.41	-2.98
3.	0.179	272.69	-948.88	-3.67
4.	0.194	342.80	-1169.55	-4.54
5.	0.203	384.88	-1478.48	-5.59
6.	0.210	407.67	-1412.28	-5.46
7.	0.216	432.33	-2008.09	-7.33

The ΔG_m^x is also ruled by enthalpy and entropy effects. The excess entropy change of mixing ΔS_m^x was generally negative (Table 4) at both the

Fig. 2. Logarithms of selectivity quotient vs Equivalent ionic fraction of iron in montmorillonite.

temperatures. ΔS_m^* could be a measure of the nature of distribution of the Na^+ and Fe^{2+} ions on the montmorillonite surface as compared to the pure forms. Its negative values for our mixed system

Acknowledgement

The second author is indebted to C.S.I.R. for the grant of a fellowship.

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Fig. 3. The excess free energy change of mixing against the equivalent fraction of Fe^{2+} ions on the clay at different temperatures.

pointed to a more ordered distribution of the mixture of Fe^{2+} and Na^+ ion on the clay surface as compared to the pure forms at all concentrations under study.